

Synthesis and Characterisation of Macrocyclic Complexes of Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Copper(II) containing a Tetradentate-N₆ Macrocyclic Ligand

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A 16-membered tetradentate N₆-macrocyclic ligand and its Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have been prepared by template method. These complexes are found to have a distorted octahedral configuration. No evidence is found for the participation of nitrogen atoms of pyridine in coordination, a fact supported by far-ir spectra. Thus the ligand coordinates through all the four azomethine nitrogen atoms.

Although a great deal of work has been carried out on the chemistry of a large number of N₄-donor systems, very little has been done on that dealing with N₆-donor and annulene types of macrocycles which show interesting geometries by virtue of the saddle shape of the molecule¹. Synthetic macrocyclic systems are considered as possible models for naturally occurring macrocyclic systems like metalloporphyrins, vitamin B₁₂ and chlorophyll². The problem of understanding the structural and electronic properties of natural and synthetic macrocyclic complexes is an elucidation of the effect of chelate ring size, ligand rigidity and extent of unsaturation. However, the central metal ion behaves in a quite different manner in different ring sizes and unsaturation.

In the present communication, the synthesis and characterisation of tetradentate N₆-macrocyclic complex of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} are described.

Results and Discussion

From the analytical data (Table 1), the complexes can be represented as M(C₄₀H₃₀N₆)X₂, where M = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}; X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, NCS⁻. The molecular weight and conductivity measurements indicate the monomeric and nonelectrolytic nature of these macrocyclic complexes. The presence of anions is evident only after decomposition of the complexes, probably due to their presence in the coordinating sphere.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra: The magnetic moments of the macrocyclic complexes of Co, Ni and Cu lie in the ranges 4.76-5.12, 3.25-3.42 and 1.75-1.84 B.M. respectively, at room temperature. The magnetic spin data shows spin-free and hexacoordinate complexes of these metals³. These macrocycles seem to have a distorted octahedral configuration.

The electronic spectra of the nickel complexes exhibit three strong bands at 10 600-12 360, 15 000-17 080 and 25 060-28 000 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at 8 500-9 600 cm⁻¹ on the low energy side of the first band⁴. The first two bands are due to the splitting of one band and can be assigned to ³B_{1g} → ³E_g (ν₁) and ³B_{1g} → ³B_{2g} (ν₂) assuming the effective symmetry D_{4h} (components of ³T_{2g} in D_h sym-

TABLE 1-ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
	C	N	H	X	M
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Cl ₂]	66.0 (66.2)	11.2 11.6	4.0 4.1	9.5 9.8	8.0 8.1
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Br ₂]	58.6 (59.0)	11.0 10.3	3.0 3.7	19.1 19.7	8.1 8.3
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂]	61.2 (61.8)	10.6 10.8	3.7 3.9	15.5 16.0	7.2 7.6
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NCS) ₂]	62.1 (62.4)	10.4 10.9	3.7 3.9	14.8 15.1	7.4 7.7
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Cl ₂]	67.1 (67.4)	11.2 11.6	4.3 4.1	9.4 9.8	7.8 8.0
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Br ₂]	59.0 (59.1)	10.0 10.3	3.4 3.6	19.6 19.7	7.0 7.1
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂]	61.2 (61.8)	10.9 10.8	4.0 3.9	15.8 16.0	7.1 7.5
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NCS) ₂]	62.3 (62.5)	10.4 10.9	3.7 3.9	14.7 15.1	7.2 7.6
[Cu(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Cl ₂]	66.7 (66.0)	11.1 11.6	4.0 4.1	9.7 9.8	8.3 8.7
[Cu(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Br ₂]	58.6 (58.8)	10.0 10.3	3.6 3.7	19.4 19.7	8.3 8.7
[Cu(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂]	61.6 (61.5)	10.6 10.8	3.7 3.8	15.4 15.9	7.8 8.1
[Cu(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NCS) ₂]	62.0 (62.2)	10.5 10.9	3.7 3.9	15.3 15.0	7.8 8.1

metry), while the higher two bands can be assigned to ³B_{1g} → ²A_{2g} (F) ³E_g (ν₃) and ³B_{1g} → ³A_{2g} (F) transitions respectively. The band appearing at 35 040 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the π → π* transition of the C=N group. A regular pattern is not followed by some of the bands. The electronic spectral data are in accord with the distorted octahedral nature of these macrocyclic complexes⁵. Thus these macrocyclic complexes exhibit a pseudo-octahedral geometry conforming to D_{4h} symmetry.

The DT/DQ ratio⁶ (Table 2) indicate distortion of the molecule and increases in the order, NCS > NO₃ > Br > Cl and are consistent with the order of the nephelauxetic series.

The electronic spectra of the copper complexes exhibit a broad band at 17 730-19 270 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder towards lower energy side at 14 500-17 720 cm⁻¹ which are

in accord with the distorted octahedral configuration⁷.

The spectra of the cobalt macrocyclic complexes show bands at 8 250–8 760 (ν_1), 15 760–16 270 (ν_2) and 21 030 cm^{-1} (broad) (ν_3). This broad band seems to consist of almost two bands at 15 520 and 21 510 cm^{-1} . The spectra of these macrocyclic complexes also show bands in the visible region which are split due to the presence of low symmetry fields. The splitting causes a band envelope due to considerable overlap and thus broad bands are observed in the spectra⁴. The various bands can be assigned on the basis of effective D_{4h} symmetry, to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (8 510 cm^{-1}), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (1 600 cm^{-1}), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (20 000 cm^{-1}). The first band ν_1 is observed near the half of the visible band and may be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g}$ (seems plausible) and it cannot be spin-forbidden⁸. The calculated values of ν_2/ν_1 , Dq , B and β (Table 2) are consistent with the accuracy of the assignment.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectral data of these macrocyclic complexes indicate that the pyridine ring and 1,3-diphenyl-2,3-propanedione moieties are present. The bands at 1 590, 1 580, 1 470 and 1 430 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ skeletal frequencies⁹, and the bands at 990, 810, 620 and 420 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ring breathing mode out-of-plane and in-plane C–C deformation mode of the pyridine ring. The strong frequencies at 1 590–1 560 cm^{-1} are often associated with CN coupled with phenyl ring vibrations. A comparison of the amine spectra shows that the strong band at 1 630 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 1 615 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric and asymmetric $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations respectively. The bands at 2 930, 1 360, 1 260, 1 180, 680 cm^{-1} and 1 610–1 440 cm^{-1} indicate that the 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione moiety is present in the macrocyclic complexes.

A close examination of the data reveals that both the

amino groups of 2,6-diaminopyridine react with oxygen atoms of 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione forming a three-carbon atom bridge between the two amino groups⁹. The spectra do not show any stretching and bending which correspond to stretching and bending of the C=O group for these complexes¹⁰. However, some changes were observed in C=N vibrations which indicate that the coordination occurs through this site⁸. Thus it may be concluded that a quadridentate macrocycle is formed having coordination through azomethine nitrogens and there is no indication of the coordination of nitrogen atom of pyridine. This idea is in accord with the fact that quadridentate macrocycles are formed more easily than hexa- or quinquidentate ligands¹¹. It is also quite interesting that the azomethine nitrogen being equally active, excludes the coordination through the pyridine nitrogen perhaps due to the formation of unstable four-membered rings.

The far-ir spectral data reveal bands at 300, 280 and 275 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to Co–Cl, Ni–Cl and Cu–Cl vibrations¹² respectively. Similarly, some bands were observed for other complexes which correspond to those of metal and axial ligand vibrations.

The spectra for nitrate complexes show bands at 1 265, 1 020, 860 cm^{-1} which are in accord with the monodentate nature of the nitrate group¹¹. The spectra of thiocyanato complexes exhibit strong bands at 2 120 (ν_1) (C=N), 485 (ν_2) (NCS bending) and 830 cm^{-1} (ν_3) (C=S of NCS group), indicating that thiocyanate groups are monodentate N-bonded. The nitrate group and the bands at 260 and 290 cm^{-1} may be assigned to (M–NCS) for these complexes. The bands at 425–495 cm^{-1} are also in accord with the involvement of the azomethine nitrogens and no (M–Py) vibration was observed in these spectral studies.¹

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	λ_{max} cm^{-1}	DQ^{xy}	DQ^z	$\frac{DT}{DQ}$	Dq^{xy}	Dq^z	D_t	DT	DS	DQ
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Cl ₂]	34 900, 27, 850, 18 200, 11 730, 10 750	32 200	26 670	0.052	1 170	970	115	1 570	11 700	30 350
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Br ₂]	34 100, 26 200, 18 240, 17 730, 11 740	32 350	26 600	0.054	1 180	969	120	1 620	11 490	30 430
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂]	35 200, 38 300, 18 300, 11 800, 10 670	32 400	26 560	0.058	1 182	950	125	1 650	11 560	30 460
[Ni(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NCS) ₂]	34 800, 28 310, 18 290, 11 700, 10 600	32 150	25 930	0.059	1 170	952	130	1 760	11 495	30 070
		Dq	B	ν_1/ν_2	β					
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(Cl ₂)]	21 600, 16 620, 15 940, 8 620	1 080	830	1.80	0.85					
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)Br ₂]	21 620, 18 500, 16 260, 8 240	1 035	810	1.98	0.88					
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NO ₃) ₂]	21 500, 18 550, 15 760, 8 600	1 070	820	1.85	0.80					
[Co(C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₆)(NCS) ₂]	21 510, 18 450, 16 100, 8 790	1 098	798	1.88	0.89					

*Calculated values of transition energy in cm^{-1}

M = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}

X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, NCS⁻

R = C₆H₅

Experimental

Solutions of 2,6-diaminopyridine (0.02 mol) and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (0.02 mol) in a minimum quantity (10 ml) of dry and cold MeOH were mixed and methanolic solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol) was added. This mixture was refluxed on a water-bath. Then concentrated HCl (1 ml) was added and further refluxed for 24 h. It was then concentrated to half of the volume and set aside for 2 days. The resulting dark coloured crystals were washed with methanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure. For the copper complexes a precipitate appeared after 6 h at the reflux temperature. The macrocyclic complexes were found stable upto 250° and soluble in H₂O, MeOH, DMF and CH₃CN except for the copper complexes being sparingly soluble in these solvents.

The nitrate complexes were prepared from metal nitrates. Bromo and thiocyanate salts were prepared by metathesis by stirring and adding slowly NaBr and NH₄NCS solutions to an ethanolic solution of metal chlorides, and NaCl or NH₄Cl formed during exchange reaction was filtered off. The metals were determined by spectrophotometric methods while halides by Volhard's nitrates gravimetrically as nitron salt. C, H and N present in the complexes were estimated microanalytically at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Punjab University, Chandigarh.

The electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss specord spectrophotometer and infrared spectra (KBr) on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer in CH₃CN as sol-

vent which had been distilled over P₄O₁₀ under nitrogen atmosphere. The conductivity was measured on a Systronics 302 instrument at 25±1° using a dip-type conductivity cell. Molecular weight was determined by freezing point depression method. Magnetic measurements were carried out using a Princeton Applied Research 155 magnetometer. The electromagnetic current was maintained using a Polytronic CP-200 constant current regulator. The instrument was calibrated using a standard pure nickel pellet and cross-checked against [HgCo(CNS)₄] as calibrant.

References

1. L. F. LINDOY and D. H. BUSCH, *Prep. Inorg. React.* 1970, 6, 1; N. F. CURTIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 3, 3; D. H. BUSCH, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1967, 174.
2. J. L. KARN and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 1149; L. F. LINDOY, N. E. TOKEL, L. B. ANDERSON and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1971, 1, 7; J. W. L. MATIN, J. H. JOHNTON and N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1967, 68; D. F. COOK and N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 1076.
3. V. B. RANA and A. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Acta Chem.*, 1974, 80, 19.
4. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
5. D. A. ROWLEY and R. S. DRAGO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 1092; R. A. D. WENTWORTH and T. S. PIPER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 4, 709, 1525.
6. J. C. DONINI, B. R. HELLEBONE and A. B. P. LEVER, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.* 1977, 22, 225.
7. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GREZESKOVIK, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1969, 5, 27.
8. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1963.
9. B. E. DOUGLAS, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1978, 18, 2.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
11. "Preparative Inorganic Reaction", eds. L. F. LINDOY and D. H. BUSCH in W. L. Jolly, 1971, Vol. 6, p. 1.
12. R. J. H. CLARK and C. S. WILLIAMS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 350.